

HONEYCOMB LIKE TEMPLATES PREPARED FROM BALSA WOOD

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Keywords: wood, cell wall, cellulose, porous

ABSTRACT

In the current study, we have used sodium chlorite and sodium hydroxide as extraction solutions, to remove lignin and hemicelluloses from the Balsa (*Ochroma Lagopus*) wood tissues, without damaging the wood honeycomb architecture. Surface morphologies are studied using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). In addition, sugars analysis of the chemically extracted wood is reported.

INTRODUCTION

Wood, with a complex hierarchical architecture, is perfectly suited as a template [1-3]. At least four distinct length scales of hierarchical order are present: wood tissue, cell structure, cell wall structural organization and cell wall polymer assembly. Wood is susceptible to cracking, dimensional instability or decay during its service period. A series of wood protection techniques have been developed for improving its performance [4].

Chemical modification of wood, which in general aims at altering molecular structures of the cell wall polymers, has been recognized as an efficient strategy for dimensional stabilization of wood and protection from environmental damage, such as deterioration due to weathering and fungal decay [5]. The typical chemical modification techniques are based on vacuum and/or high-pressure impregnation, which allows the penetration of chemicals with small molecules into wood cell wall tissue [6, 7].

Recently, porous ceramics based on combinations of pine wood and inorganic ceramics were fabricated via a sol-gel process with the use of metallic alkoxides [8-11]. Several studies have reported the pyrolysis of wood and the subsequent use of the resulting carbon materials as templates to obtain wood-derived porous ceramics [12, 13]. However, the wood composition and honeycomb architecture of these ceramic materials are completely changed which due to carbonization or structural collapse and chemical changes at high temperature during the manufacturing processes.

Various promising materials and nanocomposites have been prepared based on wood cellulose or other celluloses (i.e. bacterial cellulose or tunicate cellulose), for example nanopaper, foams and aerogels [14-21]. Another strategy in developing nanostructured materials with controlled morphologies is by the use of scaffolds or templates for directing structural growth [22]. In this work, the objective is to prepare a porous wood template (PWT) based on Balsa (*Ochroma Lagopus*). Firstly,

lignin and hemicelluloses are removed from the wood tissue, without damaging the wood honeycomb structure, which then serves as a template for preparing nanostructured composites. Herein, we report effects of delignification and hemicellulose removal, and the structures thus obtained are characterized in detail. The main challenge is to remove lignin and hemicelluloses while preserving the cell structure of Balsa.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Wood samples of Balsa (*Ochroma Lagopus*) with the dimensions of $5 \times 20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$ (longitudinal \times radial \times tangential) were prepared. Before the chemical extraction of lignin and hemicelluloses, the samples were dried at $103 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h, until a constant mass (after drying) was obtained. The experiments had been conducted on two types of samples, one which was used as a reference (where no chemical modification was done). The other balsa samples are chemically extracted with sodium chlorite (NaClO_2) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solutions respectively (Fig. 1). Finally, all the samples (which were chemically treated) were washed thoroughly with deionized water. The treated samples were frozen at -20°C overnight before they were subjected to sublimation.

Fig. 1: Schematic for the preparation of honeycomb like template.

A Hitachi SEM (S-4800) operated at 1 kV was used for the observation of cross-sections of the cell wall and cell structure. For the purpose of sugar analysis, the reference and chemically extracted samples were hydrolyzed by 3 ml of 72 wt. % of sulfuric acid solution for 2 h, then the hydrolysis solutions received addition of 84 ml deionized water respectively, and placed at 121°C for 1 h as per TAPPI T222 om-83 standards. Quantitative analysis of sugar contents, cellulose and hemicelluloses were analyzed by using a High Performance Anion Exchange Chromatography instrument (Dionex ICS-3000) equipped with pulse amperometric detector using a Dionex PA1 column.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The SEM images of the honeycomb-like cell wall architectures are shown in Fig. 2. It can be seen from the figure that there is some void space at cell wall corners (CWC) and at middle lamellae (ML) of the treated samples (Fig. 2b) in contrast to the reference samples, (Fig. 2a). This is due to the fact that in particular lignin but also hemicelluloses were extracted from the wood tissue. The emphasis is on protection of the wood honeycomb architecture after chemical extraction. It is expected that the cell wall structure is modified at a finer scale as well since the removal of lignin should result in some nanoscale porosity. The cell wall structure depends on the parameters and conditions of the treatment (for example the concentration of the solution, treatment time and temperature). Ishikura *et al.* reported that in general, the crystallinity index of wood tissue tends to be reduced at NaOH

concentrations higher than 10 wt. %. A possible explanation is structural changes in microfibrils, which alters crystal structure and degree of crystallinity. Another potential effect is mercerization, the structural transformation of cellulose from cellulose I to cellulose II at concentrations of NaOH higher than 10 wt. % [23, 24].

Fig. 2: Honeycomb like cell wall structure of (a) Balsa and (b) Balsa where lignin and hemicellulose content is reduced by chemical extraction.

Galactans and arabinogalactan hemicelluloses are distributed in middle lamella and primary cell walls in plant cells [25]. The amount of arabinose (comes from arabinogalactans) and galactose (comes from galactans) of the chemically treated samples were lower than for the native reference sample (Fig. 3), which is due to chemical removal of hemicellulose. It has been observed that the amount of glucose in treated sample (Fig. 3b) is greater as compared to untreated sample (Fig. 3a), since part of the hemicelluloses were hydrolytically degraded to small glucose molecules. Moreover, the ratio of cellulose to total tissue weight in chemically extracted samples (after the lignin and hemicellulose were removed) is much higher than for the native reference.

Fig. 3: Sugar analysis data of (a) reference and (b) chemically treated samples.

CONCLUSIONS

A method to chemically remove lignin and hemicelluloses while preserving the balsa cell structure was successfully demonstrated. Major void spaces were apparent at cell corners and middle lamella, where the lignin content is high. Nanoscale voids are expected at smaller scale. The templates are candidates for further functionalization. Galactans and arabinogalactans were removed with the help of bleaching (with NaClO_2) and alkaline (NaOH) solutions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful to the Wallenberg foundation for funding this research.

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